

Supplementary Material

As a complementary analysis to the Bayesian tests, we tested whether the organization of local elements into a global shape requires visual awareness using the NHST approach. All the analyses were performed using RStudio (Version 2022-02-03-492, RStudio, 2022, based on the R programming language Version 4.2.0, R Core Team, 2022, or higher) and the necessary R packages, which are specified below. Congruency (e.g., priming) effects on the single-task and dual-task priming blocks were analyzed using linear mixed effects models (LMM) to avoid the listwise deletion of missing values (missing data for unreported awareness levels in the dual-task priming block). Linear mixed-effect models were fitted to the data through the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2018), and statistical significance was assessed with the lmerTest package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). In the single-task priming block, Congruency was introduced as a fixed factor to the model and Participant as random effect. We intended to compare two different model fits using maximum likelihood estimation as false premise (REML = F) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC), the first model with random intercept and a model with both random intercepts and slopes ($RT \sim \text{Congruency} + (1 + \text{Congruency} | \text{Participant})$). The model with lower BIC value was expected to be chosen for the LMM analysis. The best fit between the different models would be assessed using the *anova* function of the lme4 package, which calculates the BIC values for each model and then computes a chi-square test to evaluate the best of the fitting models. In the dual-task priming block, since we are interested on how priming effects interact with subjective awareness reports, Congruency and PAS were introduced as fixed effects to the model and Participant as random effect. Here, we intended to compare a model with random intercept for participants (e.g., $RT \sim \text{Congruency} * \text{PAS} + (1 | \text{Participant})$), and a model with both random intercept and PAS slope for participants (e.g., $RT \sim \text{Congruency} * \text{PAS} + (1 + \text{Congruency} * \text{PAS} | \text{Participant})$). The model with lower BIC value would be chosen for the LMM analysis.

To explore whether the masked primes were processed without participant's awareness, prime detection responses from the prime visibility task were transformed into a sensibility measure (d'_{obj}) to produce an objective index of prime visibility. Conventional *t*-tests were calculated to understand the degree to which the evidence supported (or precluded) chance-level ($d'=0$) prime discrimination of the primes.

Results

Comments on planned linear mixed model analyses

In the single-task priming block, two different model fits were intended to be compared, the first model with random intercept and a model with both random intercepts and slopes (RT~Congruency + (1 + Congruency|Participant)). The model with lower BIC value would therefore be chosen for the LMM analysis. However, in the model with both random intercepts and slopes (RT~Congruency + (1 + Congruency|Participant)), the random-effects parameters and the residual variance (or scale parameter) were unidentifiable, due to the number of observations (=40) being equal to the number of random effects. Therefore, data was fitted using a model with random intercept only (RT~Congruency + (1|Participant)).

In the dual-task priming blocks, PAS3 and PAS4 ratings were rarely used. Furthermore, participants with more than 10 trials in both congruent and incongruent conditions for any of these two visibility ratings were a minority (ranging from 0 to 11 participants across experiments). Therefore, RT values for PAS3 and PAS4 visibility ratings were considered not to be robust, and conducting a linear mixed model with PAS as a fixed factor would not produce meaningful results. Following the logic introduced in the main article, unconscious priming effects by the global shape were explored by sending individual mean RT data for PAS1 reports (no perception of the primes) to paired sample *t*-test comparing congruent vs. incongruent trials.

Single-task analyses

Linear mixed model results indicated that Congruency effects were not significant ($F[1,19] = 0.625, p = .438, \eta^2_p = .03$) in Experiment 1 (SOA 40 ms), in line with the results reported in the main text. Results in Experiment 2 (SOA 53 ms), Experiment 3 (SOA 67 ms) and Experiment 4 (unmasked primes), showed that participants responded faster to congruent than incongruent trials (Exp. 2: $F[1,19] = 32.896, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .63$; Exp. 3: $F[1,19] = 38.281, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .67$; Exp. 4: $F[1,19] = 56.307, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .67$), also in line with the analyses reported in the main text.

Dual-task analyses

In line with the Bayesian *t*-test reported in the main article, paired NHST *t*-tests suggested no differences between congruent and incongruent trials in the three masked experiments: Exp. 1, $t(1,19) = 0.635, p = 0.533, \text{Cohen's } d = 0.142$; Exp. 2, $t(1,19) = -0.567, p = 0.577, \text{Cohen's } d = -$

0.127; Exp. 3, $t(1,19) = 0.838$, $p = 0.413$, Cohen's $d = 0.187$. Difference between congruent and incongruent trials was significant in Exp. 4 (unmasked primes), $t(1,19) = -2.520$, $p = 0.021$, Cohen's $d = -0.564$, suggesting that the priming effect when the primes were unmasked but participants reported no perception was possibly reliable.

Objective prime visibility

In line with the Bayesian t -test reported in the main article, paired NHST t -tests suggested that group visibility was not at strict chance-level (e.g., $d'=0$) in the three masked experiments: Exp. 1., $t(1,19) = 3.086$, $p = 0.006$, Cohen's $d = 0.690$; Exp. 2, $t(1,19) = 3.316$, $p = 0.004$, Cohen's $d = 0.742$; Exp. 3, $t(1,19) = 3.316$, $p = 0.018$, Cohen's $d = 0.577$. Also in line with the results reported in the main text, NHST t -test indicated that prime detection was easier when the primes were presented unmasked in Exp. 4, $t(1,19) = 9.765$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 2.184$.

References

- Bates, D., Maechler, M., Bolker, B., Walker, S., Christensen, R.H. B., Singmann, H., et al. (2018). lme4: Linear mixed-effects models using 'eigen' and S4 (R package version 1.1-17). Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/lme4/index.html>.
- Kuznetsova, A., Brockhoff, P. B., & Christensen, R. H. B. (2017). lmerTest package: Tests in linear mixed effects models. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 82, 1–26. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v082.i13>